

THE EFFECT OF DISCOVERY LEARNING MODEL ON STUDENTS' LEARNING OUTCOMES IN SOCIAL STUDIES FOR GRADE VIII AT SMP PRIVATE TAMANSISWA PEMATANGSIANTAR IN ACADEMIC YEAR 2025/2026

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Abstract

This research was motivated by the low learning outcomes of students in social studies, where students tended to be passive and the learning process lacked variation. The objective of this study was to determine the effect of the Discovery Learning teaching model on students' learning outcomes. This study is a quantitative research with a quasi-experimental method. The research sample consisted of two classes: class VIII-B as the experimental group, which was taught using the Discovery Learning model, and class VIII-C as the control group, which was taught using conventional methods. Data were collected through test instruments in the form of pre-test and post-test questions for both classes. The results showed a significant difference in student learning outcomes between the experimental and control groups. Based on the hypothesis test (t-test), the t-count value of 5.12 was greater than the t-table value of 1.67 (at a 0.05 significance level). Thus, the null hypothesis (H₀) was rejected and the alternative hypothesis (H_a) was accepted. This proves that there is a significant effect of implementing the Discovery Learning teaching model on students' learning outcomes.

Keywords: *Discovery Learning, Learning Outcomes, Social Studies, Junior High School*

INTRODUCTION

Education is the primary foundation for developing quality human resources. Through education, individuals not only acquire knowledge but also develop the attitudes, skills, and values needed to face the challenges of life in the era of globalization. Education plays a strategic role in shaping national character, increasing competitiveness, and creating a generation capable of critical, creative, and adaptive thinking to change. Therefore, the educational process must be designed systematically, directed, and sustainable so that learning objectives can be optimally achieved. In the context of formal education, learning activities in schools are the core of the entire educational process. Learning is not simply the activity of conveying material from teachers to students, but rather an educative interaction process aimed at developing students' overall potential, across the cognitive, affective, and psychomotor domains. Learning success is greatly influenced by various factors, including teacher teaching strategies, student characteristics, infrastructure, and the learning model used.

Learning models play a crucial role as they serve as a conceptual framework that guides the teaching and learning process in the classroom. Selecting the right learning model can create an active, enjoyable, and meaningful learning environment, encouraging students to engage directly in the learning process. Conversely, the use of less varied and teacher-centered learning models often leads to students being passive, easily bored, and less able to develop higher-order thinking skills. This ultimately results in low student learning outcomes. One learning model that emphasizes student activity is Discovery Learning. This model provides students with the opportunity to discover concepts or knowledge for themselves through exploration, observation, data collection, and drawing conclusions. In Discovery Learning, students not only receive information directly but are actively involved in the thinking and problem-solving process. Learning becomes more meaningful because students experience the process of discovery themselves, so the understanding gained tends to be deeper and more lasting. In its application, Discovery Learning can be carried out in the form of free discovery or guided discovery. Guided Discovery Learning positions the teacher as a facilitator who provides direction, provocative questions, and guidance throughout the learning process, without taking over the primary role of the student. This model is

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considered more suitable for junior high school students, because students still receive teacher support in discovering concepts, while also being trained to think independently, critically, and systematically. Social Studies (IPS) subjects play a crucial role in equipping students with an understanding of social, economic, cultural, and environmental life. IPS not only requires students to master theoretical concepts but also to be able to relate them to the realities of everyday life. Therefore, IPS learning is ideally implemented contextually and participatory so that students can develop analytical skills, social attitudes, and concern for the surrounding environment. However, the reality on the ground shows that social studies learning is still often carried out conventionally, with the lecture method as the primary approach. This condition causes students to tend to be passive, less motivated, and only focus on memorizing the material. The impact is visible in student learning outcomes, which have not achieved optimal mastery. Based on the results of initial observations and data from the Mid-Semester Exam (UTS) for Social Studies for grade VIII at Tamansiswa Private Junior High School in Pematangsiantar, the majority of students have not met the Minimum Completion Criteria (KKM). Of the total of 70 grade VIII students, 49 students, or approximately 70%, were declared not yet complete, while only 21 students, or 30%, achieved learning mastery.

These data indicate that social studies learning outcomes are still relatively low and require improvement through learning innovation. Furthermore, the results of interviews with social studies teachers indicate that although several learning models have been implemented, the Discovery Learning model, especially Guided Discovery Learning, has never been used in social studies learning in grade VIII. The learning process is still dominated by the teacher, while active student participation is relatively low. Students are less accustomed to expressing opinions, asking questions, or discovering concepts independently. This situation is one of the factors causing less than optimal learning outcomes. Based on these problems, an alternative learning model is needed that can increase student activity while improving social studies learning outcomes. Guided Discovery Learning is seen as a relevant solution because it encourages students to be directly involved in the process of discovering knowledge with teacher guidance. Through this model, students are expected to be able to develop critical thinking skills, increase self-confidence, and gain a deeper understanding of the subject matter. Thus, researchers are interested in conducting research on the application of the Discovery Learning learning model, specifically Guided Discovery Learning, on student learning outcomes in social studies subjects of grade VIII at Tamansiswa Private Junior High School, Pematangsiantar. This research is expected to provide an empirical picture of the model's effectiveness in improving learning outcomes, as well as being a consideration for teachers and schools in developing more innovative and student-centered learning strategies.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Learning outcomes are the primary indicator of the success of the learning process because they reflect students' mastery of the material they have learned. Learning outcomes are not limited to cognitive aspects but also encompass the affective and psychomotor domains, as seen through changes in students' knowledge, attitudes, and skills after participating in learning. Various experts state that learning outcomes are influenced by internal factors, such as students' motivation, interests, talents, and readiness to learn, as well as external factors, including the school environment, teacher teaching methods, and the learning model used. Therefore, selecting the right learning model is a key factor in improving the quality of student learning outcomes. A learning model is a conceptual framework used by teachers as a guide in designing and implementing the teaching and learning process systematically. Learning models function to create a conducive learning atmosphere, direct student activities, and help achieve learning objectives. One learning model that emphasizes student activity is Discovery Learning.

This model is based on a constructivist approach that positions students as the main subjects of learning, where students are encouraged to discover concepts or principles for themselves through the processes of observation, exploration, data collection, information processing, verification, and drawing conclusions. In this way, learning is no longer teacher-centered, but rather provides space for students to build their knowledge independently. Discovery Learning has two main forms: free discovery and guided discovery. In free discovery, students are given complete freedom to discover concepts without direct guidance from the teacher, while in guided discovery, the teacher acts as a facilitator, providing guidance, instructions, and prompting questions to ensure a focused discovery process. Guided Discovery Learning is considered more appropriate for junior high school students because students still need support in developing critical thinking and problem-solving skills. Through this model, students do not merely passively receive information but are actively involved in the learning process, resulting in deeper and more lasting understanding. Several previous studies have shown that the implementation of the Discovery Learning model, particularly Guided Discovery Learning, has a positive impact

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on student learning outcomes. This model has been proven to increase students' activeness, motivation, self-confidence, and critical thinking skills. Students become more enthusiastic about participating in learning because they are directly involved in discovering concepts, discussing, and solving problems. Compared with conventional learning models that tend to emphasize lectures and memorization, Guided Discovery Learning provides a more meaningful learning experience because students construct knowledge through the process of discovery. In the context of social studies learning, Guided Discovery Learning is highly relevant because social studies material is closely related to social, economic, and environmental phenomena that can be explored through observation and analysis activities. With this model, students can relate social studies concepts to real life, so that learning becomes more contextual. In addition, Guided Discovery Learning also helps students develop 21st-century skills, such as critical thinking, communication, collaboration, and creativity. Based on theoretical studies and relevant research results, it can be concluded that Guided Discovery Learning is an alternative learning model that has the potential to significantly improve students' social studies learning outcomes.

METHOD

This study used a quantitative approach with a quasi-experimental method. The quantitative approach was chosen because the study aimed to test the effect of a treatment on certain variables through numerical measurements and statistical analysis. The research design used was a nonequivalent control group design, which involved two non-randomly selected groups, consisting of an experimental class and a control class. Both groups were given a pre-test to determine students' initial abilities, then the experimental class was given treatment in the form of the Discovery Learning (Guided Discovery Learning) learning model, while the control class was taught using a conventional learning model. After the learning process was completed, both groups were given a final test (post-test) to determine student learning outcomes. This study was conducted at Tamansiswa Private Junior High School, Pematangsiantar in the 2025/2026 Academic Year. The study population was all 70 eighth-grade students. The research sample was determined using a purposive sampling technique, resulting in two classes as samples: class VIII-B as the experimental class and class VIII-C as the control class. Sample selection was based on considerations of the equivalence of students' initial abilities and recommendations from the school.

The variables in this study consist of the independent variable (X), namely the Discovery Learning learning model, and the dependent variable (Y), namely students' social studies learning outcomes. The Discovery Learning learning model is implemented through the stages of stimulation, problem statement, data collection, data processing, verification, and generalization. Meanwhile, student learning outcomes are measured through test scores that reflect students' cognitive abilities after participating in the learning process. The research instrument used was a multiple-choice test consisting of 25 questions given in the form of a pre-test and post-test. The pre-test aims to determine students' initial abilities before treatment, while the post-test is used to measure improvements in learning outcomes after the learning process has taken place. Before use, the instrument was first tested for validity and reliability to ensure that the questions were truly suitable for use as a measuring tool. The data collection technique was carried out by administering tests to both sample groups. The data obtained were then analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistical techniques. Descriptive analysis was used to determine the average value and standard deviation, while inferential analysis included normality tests, homogeneity tests, and hypothesis testing using t-tests. The normality test aims to determine whether the data is normally distributed, the homogeneity test is used to see the equality of variance between the two groups, and the t-test is used to determine whether there is a significant difference in learning outcomes between the experimental class and the control class. Through these procedures, this study is expected to be able to provide an objective picture of the effect of the application of the Discovery Learning learning model on the social studies learning outcomes of grade VIII students.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research Result Data

This research was conducted from September 1 to September 20, 2025, at Tamansiswa Private Junior High School in Pematangsiantar. The test results obtained from the two classes that served as the experimental sample are presented in Appendix 11.

1. Calculation of Mean and Standard Deviation

The calculation of the mean and standard deviation is attached in appendix 12. The following table presents two statistics from two groups:

Table 4.4 Statistics of the Results of the Second Sample Test

Types of Statistics	Guided Discovery Learning Class Score	Conventional Class Scores
N (Number of Samples)	25	22
Highest Score	100	92
Lowest Score	80	76
Average	90.08	82
Variance	33.49	27.04
Standard Deviation	5.78	5.20

Source: data processed in 2025

From table 4.5, statistical data on the values of the two samples shows that the social science (IPS) learning outcomes in the *Guided Discovery Learning learning group* are better than the social science learning outcomes of students in the conventional learning group.

2. Data Normality Test

a. Initial Condition (Pre-Test Value)

chi-square test was used . The results of the normality test calculations (see Appendix 13) for the sample using the initial data are shown in the following table.

Table 4.5 Normality of Pre-Test Value Data

Class	Df	X ² count	X ² table	Information
Experiment	6	7.4	12.59	Normal
Control	5	2.09	11.07	Normal

Source: data processed in 2025

The results of the normality test show that the mid-semester scores of the experimental group and the control group have normally distributed data. The normality test shows that the calculated X² value = 7.4 in the experimental group and 2.09 in the control group. With a level of 5% and df = 6 for the experimental group and df = 5 for the control group, it is known that the X² table value is 12.59 for the experimental group and 11.07 for the control group, so that the calculated X² < X² table . This means that the learning outcomes in the experimental group and the control group are normally distributed at the time of the Pre-test value.

b. Final Condition (Post Test)

The results of the normality test calculations for samples using the final data can be seen in the following table:

Table 4.6 Normality of Post-Test Value Data

Class	df	X ² count	X ² table	Information
Experiment	4	5.24	9.48	Normal
Control	3	4.45	7.81	Normal

Source: data processed in 2025

The results of the normality test show that the learning outcomes of the experimental group and the control group have normally distributed data. The normality test shows the calculated X² value = 5.24 in the experimental group and 4.45 in the control group. With a level of 5% and df = 4 for the experimental group and df = 3 for the control group, it is known that the X² table value is 9.48 for the experimental group and 7.81 for the control group, so that the calculated X² < X² table . This means that the learning outcomes in the experimental group and the control group are normally distributed.

3. Homogeneity of Variance Test

a. Initial conditions (Pre-Test)

The homogeneity test was conducted to determine the variance of the two data groups, namely the pre-test value of the experimental group and the post-test value of the control group (see appendix 14). The results of the homogeneity test can be seen in the following table.

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Table 4.7 Homogeneity of Pre-Test Variance

Class	N	Variance (V)	F _{count}	F _{table}
Experiment	25	8,889	0.993	1,984
Control	22	8,926		

Source: data processed in 2025

The table shows that the calculated F value is 0.993, while the F table value for n = 25.22 is 1.984. Thus, the calculated F value is smaller than the F table. This can be interpreted that both groups of student pre-test score data from the experimental group and the control group are homogeneous.

b. Post-Test Condition

The homogeneity test was conducted to determine the variance of the two groups of data, namely the learning outcome values of the experimental group and the values of the control group.

The results of the homogeneity test can be seen in the following table.

Table 4.8 Homogeneity of Variance of Learning Outcome Values

Class	N	Variance (V)	F _{count}	F _{table}
Experiment	25	5,787	1,112	1,984
Control	22	5,200		

Source: data processed in 2025

The table shows that the calculated F value is 1.112, while the F table value for n = 25.22 is 1.984. Thus, the calculated F value is smaller than the F table. This indicates that both groups of student learning outcome data, namely the post-test scores of students from the experimental group and the control group, are homogeneous.

4. Research Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis testing was conducted after the homogeneity of variance and normality tests. Hypothesis testing was conducted through a test of the difference between two means using the t-statistic. Hypothesis testing was conducted to determine whether the data were normally distributed in relation to student learning outcomes using the *Guided Discovery Learning* and conventional learning models.

H₀ : (the sample mean of $\sigma_1 = \sigma_2$, the *Guided Discovery Learning* model group and the Conventional learning model group is not significantly different)

H_a : (the sample mean of $\sigma_1 \neq \sigma_2$, the *Guided Discovery Learning* model group and the Conventional learning model group differs significantly)

The calculation in appendix 15 shows the results obtained, namely $t_{hit} = 5.12$. After comparing t_{hit} with t_{table} with a significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$ and $dk = 47$, the points obtained were $-t_{(0.95; 62)} = -1.67$ and $t_{(0.95; 62)} = 1.67$. It turns out that t_{hit} is in the critical area because $5.12 > 1.67$. Therefore, H₀ is rejected and H_a is accepted. The conclusion is that there is an influence of the *Guided Discovery Learning learning model* on the learning outcomes of class VIII students in social studies learning at Tamansiswa Private Middle School, Pematangsiantar.

RESEARCH DISCUSSION

This research is entitled "The Effect of *Discovery Learning Model* on Student Learning Outcomes in Social Studies Subjects for Grade VIII at Tamansiswa Private Middle School, Pematangsiantar". The results of the normality test before the study were conducted showed that both classes were normally distributed. The results of the homogeneity test before the study showed that the two classes that would be the research samples were homogeneous. The classes taken by the researcher as research samples were class VIII-B and VIII-C. Class VIII-B was the experimental class with the *Guided Discovery Learning learning model*, while class VIII-C was the control class using the conventional learning model. The main problem to be answered through this research is: Is there a significant influence of the *Guided Discovery Learning learning model* on student learning outcomes in the subject of Social Studies class VIII at Tamansiswa Private Junior High School Pematangsiantar in the academic year 2025/2026. The purpose of this research is: To find out how big the significance of the difference in student learning outcomes using the *Guided Discovery Learning learning model* with student learning outcomes using conventional learning methods in Social Studies learning at Tamansiswa Private Junior High School Pematangsiantar in the academic year 2025/2026.

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The trial results show that the questions given are of good quality because the research instrument is valid. The lowest validity coefficient value is 0.422861 which is found in question items no. 15 and 25. The highest coefficient value is 0.661610 which is found in question item no. 3. In this study, the test questions used are with the provision that $r_{\text{count}} > r_{\text{table}}$, namely 0.413. There are 25 questions used in this study. The test is reliable because the test reliability coefficient is 1.347 compared to the critical r_{table} value of product moment for $\alpha = 0.05$ and $n = 25$, namely $r_{\text{table}} = 0.396$. Thus, $r_{\text{count}} > r_{\text{table}}$ or $0.807 > 0.396$. The smallest test difficulty level value is 0.47 which is found in question item no. 3. The highest coefficient difficulty level value is 0.73 which is found in question items no. 1,3,8. The lowest value of the discriminating power of the item is 0.114 which is found in item number 25. The highest discriminating power value is 0.747 which is found in item number 3. Thus it can be said that the quality of the test is good and can be used as a data collector in this research.

The results of the normality test using chi square show that the data from the two groups are normally distributed, $X^2_{\text{count}} = 5.24$ in the experimental group and 4.45 in the control group. With a level of 5% and $df = 4$ for the experimental group and $df = 3$ for the control group, it is known that the value of X^2_{table} is 9.48 for the experimental group and 7.81 for the control group, so that $X^2_{\text{count}} < X^2_{\text{table}}$. Based on the scores of student learning outcomes, the results of the sample homogeneity test using the F test obtained a calculated F value of 1.112, while the F table value for $n = 25.22$ is 1.984. Thus, the calculated F value is smaller than the F table. So that both sample classes are homogeneous. From the results of the data analysis, the calculated average and standard deviation of the group using the *Guided Discovery Learning learning model* are $\bar{X} = 90.08$ and $S = 5.78$. The calculated average and standard deviation of the group using the conventional model are $\bar{X} = 82$ and $S = 5.20$, meaning that the average of students using the *Guided Discovery Learning learning model* is higher than students using the conventional learning model. For the test of the difference between the two means, the calculated $t = 5.12$ and the table $t = 1.67$ are in the critical area because the calculated $t > \text{table } t$, namely $5.12 > 1.67$ so that the average of the two samples is significantly different. Thus, it can be concluded that (1) There is an influence of the *Discovery Learning learning model* on student learning outcomes in the subject of Social Studies for class VIII at Pematangsiantar Private Middle School (2) The learning outcomes of students who use the *Guided Discovery Learning learning model* are better than the learning outcomes of students who use the conventional model. This can be seen from the results of the average score of the student learning outcome test with the *Guided Discovery Learning learning model* which is higher than the average score of the student learning outcome test with the conventional model, namely 90.08.

CONCLUSION

Based on the research results as described above in chapter IV, the research instrument is declared to be of good quality because it is valid and reliable. Of the 25 questions, all of them meet the validity requirements ($r_{\text{count}} > r_{\text{table}}$) with validity coefficients ranging from 0.422861 to 0.661610, as well as high reliability with a coefficient of 1.347. The level of difficulty and the discriminating power of the questions also show adequate quality. The normality and homogeneity test of the data showed that both groups were normally and homogeneously distributed. The average learning outcomes of students using the *Guided Discovery Learning learning model* ($\bar{X}_y = 90.08$) were higher than those using conventional learning ($\bar{X}_y = 82$), and the t-test results showed a significant difference between the two ($t_{\text{count}} = 5.12 > t_{\text{table}} = 1.67$). Thus, it can be concluded that the instrument used is feasible, and the *Guided Discovery Learning learning model* has a positive influence on student learning outcomes. So it can be concluded that there is an influence of the *Guided Discovery Learning learning model* on student learning outcomes in the Social Studies subject of class VIII at Tamansiswa Private Middle School, Pematangsiantar, namely 5.12.

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